

Factors Affecting Use of Expense Information on Financial Statements in Viet Nam Agricultural Enterprises

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Abstract:

Vietnam increasingly integrates into the international economy, so the competitive environment at home and abroad of agricultural enterprises (DN) is increasingly fierce. In order to survive and thrive in such an environment, an agricultural enterprise must have necessary information for governance, especially cost information (CI). Therefore, the use of cost information (UCI) for administration is an important and urgent issue. The result of the study show the impact of factors on UCI, respectively: cost management, information technology (IT), CI role and managerial support.

Keywords: Using information on costs, activity results, agribusinesses

1. Introduction

Vietnam is increasingly integrating internationally, so the competitive environment at home and abroad of enterprises (DN) is increasingly fierce. In order to survive and thrive in such an environment, enterprises must have governance capacity to compete and develop. For management, the manager must have the necessary information, an innovative governance perspective is cost information (CI). Given the importance of CI, current research has appreciated the role of CI in governance, Gagne & Discenza (1993) reports that car manufacturers that used CI goals have achieved benefits from cost reduction and increased profits. Similar to this point of view, Cooper & Slagmulder (1999) argue that using CI targets, in which costs are divided among regions, which are responsible for cutting costs, help ensure that only New profitable products are brought to the market. In addition, CI from other perspectives also shows the ability to estimate costs to use in product pricing and point out areas that need to be changed in the business process in order to cut costs. This allows the company to better respond to customer desires (Kaplan & Cooper, 1998). In terms of decision making, according to Brierley (2008), CI can be used for decision making, the ability to provide information about the profit and loss of each product, customer and use it for administrative purposes about decisions. plan to add or remove a certain product.

Agri-businesses should assess the factors affecting their use of cost information in their financial reporting system. From there give the right solutions.

Existing research abroad on the use of cost information (UCI) and the benefits of CI contributing to improve performance (PER) has also been performed quite a lot. However, the studies mainly use the case method and descriptive statistics such as Gagne & Discenza (1993), Cooper & Slagmulder (1999). Therefore, even abroad, this research direction also needs to supplement quantitative research model to measure the impact of UCI on PER. In addition, the research direction of factors affecting UCI focuses mainly on factors outside the enterprise, while the internal factors of enterprises are less mentioned, so it is necessary to supplement focused studies. explore factors within enterprises that affect UCI. Studies on UCI impacting PER often focus on UCI in enterprises that apply ABC (Activity based costing - ABC).

2. Literature review

Research on domestic and international cost accounting system (CAS) related to CAS development process. The first stage of development is the traditional CAS that provides cost information of fabricated products using the total cost (also known as Absorption Costing) method. On this platform, the CI provides governance such as estimation, CVP analysis, volatility analysis, selling price decision and other governance issues. The next stage of development is when the business environment has many changes such as information technology (IT), production technology, the pressure of domestic and international competition becomes more severe, it requires processing and supply. Information management in general and CI in particular becomes an essential and urgent

need. The traditional CAS is starting to become outdated and changes in new approaches are needed to meet the information needs required by the administrator in the new environment. During this period, there emerged CAS studies following new approach, in which the outstanding method was ABC (Activity Based Costing).

Hornngren et al. (2012) introduced the relationship between accounting and governance functions in terms of (a) planning, (b) pricing decision, (c) control and (d) evaluation. result pricing and decision making. Studies on the uses and benefits of CI in governance are mainly focused on these governance functions.

First of all, the researches on UCI serving the planning function, most notably using CI in Japan, Gagne & Discenza (1993) said that in Japan, due to the highly competitive nature of the In car manufacturing, cost reduction in the planning and design phases is an important management issue. Japanese car companies have to calculate 100% of product costs in the planning and design stages. Product features and functions are identified and the members of the product project team set the target selling price that the market will accept. Japanese car companies have discovered that using CI targets has had great benefits, that is, cost reduction for regions and parts with high potential to reduce costs, from that increases profit.

Similarly, Leahy (1998) through a fairly convincing data on target CI use, the author found that between 10% and 20% of the costs were cut from using target CI, from there. concludes that the use of CI targets can cut costs, bring higher profits, greater competitiveness. This study also explores the role of the target CI in increasing customer satisfaction, employee satisfaction, and better engagement with stakeholders and partners.

Another study is to analyze the use of target CI in cost allocation in the planning and product development phase. Cooper & Slagmulder (1999) collected data in manufacturing enterprises in Japan to evaluate how the target CI role in governance is, the study argues that the use of target CI through the allocation of target costs spending on regions responsible for cost-cutting, which helps ensure that only profitable products reach the market. This is the research that has made a key finding about UCI in the planning and product development phase.

More recent studies on target CI use are covered by Matarneh & El-Dalabeeh (2016) to identify target CI use in product cost reduction, as well as in determining role. CI's goals in product development at companies in Jordan. The analysis results show that using target CI leads to cost reduction, linking target CI with product quality aspect to achieve cost savings so that the product has advantages over other competitor's product.

Mustafa & El- Dalahmeh (2018) identify target use of CI to reduce costs of Jordanian companies for the food industry. To achieve the research objective, the researcher uses standard deviation and t-test methods. Survey results show the importance of using target CI to manage costs and improve profitability. Similarly, Baharudin & Jusoh (2019) this study provides an empirical study on the use of target CI, the results indicate that target CI has helped Malaysian automakers increase their ability to manage and organize regulation. submit.

Most of the previous studies were quite similar in their approach, which was repetitive, mainly statistics on the role and benefits of the target CI to the PER, or by the case method in a most industry group. concentration. Recently, the study of Ilemona & Sunday (2019) showed a change in approach and started to use quantitative methods to consider the impact of using CI targets on the profitability of enterprises. This study examined the impact of target CI use on the success of a Nigerian producer. The purpose of the study is to define the role of the target CI in terms of product cost and profitability in Nigeria. Use a questionnaire designed on a five-point Likert scale to survey textile companies operating in the northwestern states of Nigeria. The study uses a single regression with the dependent variable of profit and the target CI as the independent variable. The results show that target CI has a significant impact on profits, from which the study recommends using target CI for production firms in Nigeria to reduce costs, produce more quality, and increase competitiveness. competition, increase sales, increase profits and succeed in business.

Another direction of research is on UCI, this one focuses on UCI on the operational basis for control. Chongruksut (2002) researching UCI in Thai enterprises found that CI from ABC will help enterprises to control costs better and support cost-cutting efforts. The benefits received from the CI according to ABC are increased competitiveness and profitability. Findings about factors affecting CI use from ABC system are also explored, which is the need for managers' support such as training, training and rewarding. Other departments in the company must also understand the r goal of ABC, the cohesion between the CI designer and users from the

ABC system.

The same research direction as Chongruksut (2002) but in a different context is India through the study of Anand et al. (2005), the author affirms that enterprises have succeeded in achieving accurate CI from ABC system. Besides, the necessity of CI activities for the purpose of estimating, deciding product selling prices and analyzing customer profitability was satisfied by the Indian managers from the ABC system.

Next, Shil & Pramanik (2012) thinks that CI from ABC will help businesses improve decision making, analyze and control product profits, better measure PER and improve operations. Along this line of research, a series of studies go into analysis and evaluation to determine the role of CI in governance, such as Cinquini et al., (2008), Uyar (2010), Tobi et al. (2015), Almeida & Cunha (2017) raised the need for CI in governance such as support for estimating, deciding product prices, analyzing customer profits, rewarding, deciding to make or buy in addition, the transfer price. In general, the studies towards ABC are similar to the approach of the studies on using CI in enterprises, mainly descriptive statistics or case studies about UCI and the benefits of UCI in Administration for different purposes.

Research on factors affecting UCI:

The first research mentioned is Khandwalla (1972) research on competition affecting UCI, the author thinks that information provided for management control is provided mostly from the accounting system. The higher the level of competition, the higher the need for cost control, especially businesses that use CI to set up a flexible budget, affected by the intensity of competition.

The study related to cost management influencing use and indirect cost analysis is explored by Miller & Vollmann (1985), the authors suggest that cost drivers explain They are relatively reasonable in forecasting inputs and they have very high economic implications for governance. Managers need to make relatively accurate forecasts about the resources to produce products and model the underlying relationship between the factors that generate the costs of activities, the costs of operations and production. products for managers to understand, explain thoroughly and manage the balance between the benefits of deciding to sell products to customers and the costs of the complex operations of manufacturing and providing services (Shank, 1989). A similarly implied finding by Ittner & MacDuffie (1995) suggests that when changes in the cost factors lead to changes in the need for direct labor resources, this leads to indirect resource changes in worker supervision and management.

Competitive factors continue to be considered for impact on UCI during the planning phase. Studies focus on examining the impact on target CI use in Japan. Tani et al. (1994) made an important finding that many companies now prepare cost estimates right in the design phase. There is a connection between the product designer and the CAS, both of which share the database together to achieve the target CI. In general, the best manufacturers in the world have a clear market orientation for product development that tends to use targeted CI. Similarly, a series of studies of factors affecting the use of CI targets, such as Boer & Ettl (1999), Butscher & Laker (2000), Hibbets et al. (2003) showed that the target CI is suitable for companies operating in competitive environments and with short product life cycles.

A leader factor is also explored in influencing the use of target CI. Bhimani & Neike (1999), reporting on target CI usage at Siemens, found that the use of target CI is influenced by governance factors such as planning, product redesign decisions product and manufacturing process design. In addition, Koga (1999) discovered two behavioral variables that lead to lower product costs (i) frequent interactions between product designers and manufacturing engineers and (ii) participation. of lead in project management in the early stages of product development.

Factors about the manager's support in terms of funding also have an impact on the enterprise UCI. Geiger & Ittner (1996) examines the impact of the competitive environment while also looking at the resource support factor on UCI in public sector organizations. The author analyzes and examines the factors that influence the design and UCI of public organizations. It is through empirical evidence that these organizations use CI to comply with statutory requirements. In addition, public institutions, which are allowed to be financially autonomous and have revenues and expenses, use CI more than units covered by the budget. This means that the element of competition and funding resources has an impact on UCI of public sector organizations. In

addition, these organizations also tend to use CI widely for many purposes from price decision to management control.

Research on the relationship between CI use and supply chain governance is conducted by Ellram (2002). According to Ellram, supply chain management plays an important role, especially in the early stages of setting the target CI of the components in the product. Supply chain management also plays a big role in managing, monitoring, and improving costs. Ellram found that offering a target price to the suppliers, this encourages them to be more competitive. Supplier participation is also important because certain changes can have a major impact on a supplier's price. Vendor involvement also enhances the purchasing organization's level of goal CI. In addition, Lockamy & Smith (2000) sees the target CI as a means to integrate customer feedback in the supply chain through the development of an overall cost structure according to requirements. demand from existing customers.

3. Theory

3.1. Management Control Systems (MCS)

The Management Control System (MCS), introduced by Anthony (1965), defined that as the process of ensuring that resources are obtained and used effectively and efficiently in fulfilling their goals. organization. Hence, the concept of control in organizations is often related to the existence of certain objectives in all organizations. Otley (1999) also pointed out that MCS provides useful information for managers to do their work and help organizations grow. Furthermore, any evaluation of the role of information requires that the manager's use of the information be taken into account.

Randomized studies have focused on many aspects of the MCS. These include examining the design and implementation of CASs such as ABC / M with critical scenarios related to successful implementation (Anderson & Young, 1999; Chenhall, 2003; Foster & Swenson, 1997; Kennedy & Affleck -Graves, 2001; Shields, 1995). Research on the output of the MCS can be broken down into related issues such as the use or usefulness of the MCS, behavioral outcomes, and the organization. There is an ambiguity between these results, if MCS is found to be helpful then it is likely that they will be used and provided satisfaction by individuals, resulting in these individuals making decisions. improve and achieve better organizational goals. Obviously, MCS is useful, thereby improving job satisfaction and improving the organization's PER. Accordingly, MCS studies are based on usage (Anderson & Young, 1999; Foster & Swenson, 1997), usefulness of information (Chenhall, 1986; Shields, 1995), importance for development. products (Davila, 2000), and satisfaction with systems (Ittner & Larcker, 1997).

3.2. Management Information Systems (MIS)

Lee (2001) defined MIS as a system or process that provides the information needed to manage organizations effectively. In addition, Baskerville & Myers (2002) defines MIS as the development, use and application of information systems of individuals, organizations and society. MIS is a system that includes a network of all communication channels used in an organization. Laudon & Laudon (2003) defined MIS as a study of information systems focused on their use in business and management. The above definitions show that MIS has emphasized the development, application and validation of relevant theories and models in data processing to deliver a management reporting system about a team's activities. function, providing information and feedback to management. Recently, Adebayo (2007) explained that the existence of MIS is needed to improve and enhance decision-making on matters affecting human and material resources.

3.3. Agency Theory (Agency Theory)

Representative theory is derived from economic information theories. At the simplest level, agency theory focuses on answering two questions: (i) how information systems, accounting, and rewarding affect employee motivation and (ii) do how employee motivation issues impact information design, accounting and reward system. As such, accounting and other information is placed into a context for management and decision-making. The value of information for better management and decision making (higher returns) is the result of its use.

International Audit deals with measurement and information issues in a business. This information is used to help evaluate past decisions as well as efforts to improve future decisions. These decisions include the allocation of resources in a business, coordination among departments within the enterprise, prices, costs, and reward policies. There are many ways in which this information is provided through budgets, CASs, transfer pricing systems and measures of performance (both financial and non-financial). The initial application of representative theory in accounting research is Demski & Feltham (1979), Butterworth & Falk (1986), researchers have strongly argued and give a view that representatives occupy A key role in measuring performance and setting the terms to be achieved in a company. Next, the study of Banker & Datar (1989) mentioned the development of metrics to evaluate the policy of rewarding management performance. The regression analysis shows that PER measures based on net return will only be optimized if the correct estimates of cost and revenue sensitivity are equal. In a study of the choice of the PER measurement system for remuneration policy, Ittner et al. (1997) concluded, using non-financial metrics to increase the level of regulation, content of the trend of renewing corporate strategy, approving initiatives to improve strategic quality.

4. Research Methodology

Research topics are conducted according to mixed methods, including qualitative and quantitative.

Qualitative research: The first step is the author of the thesis to select, analyze and synthesize from previous studies to find research gaps. In this step, the most important thing is to find out the main research concept from which to sketch out the expected research model, including independent, dependent variables and relationships among variables through research hypotheses. assist. In the next step, the author builds a draft scale for the independent and dependent variables in the research model. To build scales for variables, the author of the thesis selects and synthesizes from previous studies to build a draft scale. The next step is qualitative research through interviews with a number of experts to determine the suitability of the model, draft scales in Vietnamese conditions.

□ Quantitative research: testing the scale by analyzing the reliability of $Cr\alpha$ and EFA to form a set of scales for the research model. The scales continue to be tested by CFA affirmative factor analysis to prepare for research model testing. After testing the scale in the research model, the research model and hypothesis are tested by the SEM linear structure model. In addition, the Bootstrap method is used to verify the reliability of the estimates in the official research model.

□ Factor analysis to discover EFA

To test scientific hypotheses, first of all, it is necessary to evaluate the reliability and value of the scale. In which, the $Cr\alpha$ method is used to evaluate the reliability of the scale, while the EFA analysis method helps us determine the convergence value and the discriminant value of the scale. Accordingly, it is necessary to consider important attributes in the EFA results, according to Nguyen Dinh Tho (2011), the requirements when analyzing the EFA are: (1) KMO coefficient, (2) the number of extracted factors, (3) factor weights and (4) total extracted variance (AVE).

The KMO coefficient (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) is an index used to evaluate the appropriateness of the EFA analysis and is required to be satisfactory with an indicator of $0.5 \leq KMO \leq 1$, Bartlett Test is statistically significant with the indicator Sig. <0.05 , indicates a percentage of overall variance as Percentage of variance $> 50\%$. Number of extraction factors: With this indicator, the number of factors determined in the stationary factor with the Eigen-value indicator is at least 1 ($> = 1$). Factor weight: in EFA analysis, the factor weight of a variable of that factor is required to be high, in the process of testing the factor weight standard, it is necessary to ensure the following indicators: (a) the load factor > 0.3 is considered to be the minimum, (b) the load factor > 0.4 is considered relatively important,

(c) load factor > 0.5 is considered to be of practical significance. Generally, a factor weight of a variable $> = 0.5$ is acceptable. Total variance extracted (AVE): If the total of this AVE is 50% or more, it is considered good if the total of AVE is 60% or more. If these criteria are met, we can conclude that the analysis of the EFA model is appropriate.

Research models

Fig. 1. Research model

Research theories

- H1: The CI role has a positive (+) side effect on UCI.
- H2: Cost management has a positive (+) side effect on UCI.
- H3: IT has a positive impact (+) on UCI.
- H4: Manager's support having a positive (+) positive impact on UCI.

5. Research results

Table 1: EFA and independent factors affecting UCI

KMO and Bartlett's Test: 0.833				
Total Variance Explained: 70.201				
Rotated Component Matrix^a				
	Component			
	1	2	3	4
MPPDV2	.855			
MPPDV5	.842			
MPPDV4	.799			
MPPDV1	.790			
MPPDV3	.790			
HTNQL5		.888		
HTNQL2		.816		
HTNQL1		.800		
HTNQL4		.789		
HTNQL3		.750		
TQTTTCP4			.890	
TQTTTCP2			.854	
TQTTTCP1			.808	
TQTTTCP3			.736	
CNTT3				.871
CNTT4				.836
CNTT2				.829
CNTT1				.756

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Table 2: EFA, UCI scale

KMO and Bartlett's Test: 0.830				
Total Variance Explained: 64.507				
Rotated Component Matrix ^a				
	Component			
	1	2	3	4
KS3	.827			
KS1	.816			
KS5	.770			
KS4	.751			
KS2	.711			
KS6	.696			
KH4		.865		
KH3		.853		
KH2		.821		
KH1		.664		
DGTHRQD1			.829	
DGTHRQD4			.815	
DGTHRQD3			.750	
DGTHRQD2			.694	
QDG1				.910
QDG3				.851
QDG2				.704
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.				

The following section presents the CFA results of the independent factors that impact on UCI including: CI role, cost management, IT and manager support.

Chi-square=228.369 ; df=129 ; P=.000;
 Chi-square/df=1.770 ;
 GFI=.905 ; TLI=.945 ; CFI=.954 ;
 RMSEA=.058

6. Conclusion

The scale of the role of CI, IT, and support of the manager with statistical indicators is satisfactory. Moreover, in terms of the content of the scale, the previous studies all support the observed variables of this scale. For the cost management scale that was limited to the research scope, it was marketing, distribution and after-sales services. The value chain cost management has many phases: research, design, production, marketing, distribution and after-sales service, whereby the thesis author only chooses a cost management scale in the period. marketing, distribution and after-sales service. However, if you expand the scale of cost management for the research, design, production and other functions in the value chain, it is necessary to re-test the scale to meet the research objectives for each case. Specifically. In general, with this result, the scale of CI, cost management, IT, and managerial support is satisfactory when analyzing Crα, EFA, CFA, this proves that the scale is consistent with market data. Vietnam.

The UCI Scale is a tier 2 multidirectional scale, consisting of four components, including planning, pricing decisions, controlling, and evaluating results and decision making. In this study, the author of the dissertation focuses on researching UCI factors for governance, so the scale should be adjusted to a level 2 scale to clarify the factors affecting the level of UCI for governance and their influence. of UCI to PER. If the UCI concept for governance is used in the research on measuring the success and efficiency of CAS, then the UCI concept for governance can use the first order scale as suggested by previous researchers such as Triest & Elshahat (2007), Shoute (2009), Mahama & Cheng (2013), because using the second order scale in this case can increase the complexity of the research concept in measuring success. publicity and efficiency of the CAS. Thus, the use of the UCI concept for level 1 or 2 management depends on each specific case study that the researcher chooses the scale accordingly. Another problem is that, depending on the researcher perspective, approach and purpose, the UCI conceptual scale for governance can be set up in many different ways, for example, UCI by value chain. includes components: research and development, design, production, marketing, distribution and after-sales service. Either approach environmental accounting, or the sustainable development accounting approach, the UCI is set up to suit the research approach, context, content and objective.

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